

D3.2 (M24) Report on annual training events for professional Data Stewards and monthly BioMedData RI-PAL meetings (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - Strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR

Project duration: 2022-04-01 - 2026-03-31 (48 months)

Funder: The Research Council of Norway

Project number: [322392](#)

Report prepared by: Korbinian Bösl, Nazeefa Fatima, Federico Bianchini

Publication date: 1. April 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10911355](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10911355)

Keywords: Data Management, Data Steward, Training, Data Stewardship, Life Sciences

Context

ELIXIR Norway is a vital part of the European research infrastructure for life science data and plays a crucial role in enabling data-driven innovation in the Norwegian life science landscape. The training events on data management and the monthly BioMedData meetings with the Research Infrastructure Project Area Liaisons (RI PALs) are instrumental in fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and skill development among the community.

The events listed below reflect the commitment of ELIXIR Norway and the BioMedData project towards advancing data management, data stewardship, and FAIR principles in the field of life sciences across Norway. These events serve as platforms for sharing best practices in research data management, discussing challenges, and promoting the adoption of standardised data management routines. They also contribute to building a network of skilled professionals who are essential in ensuring the quality, integrity, and accessibility of life science data.

Activities

List of events carried out during the period 2022-present.

Event Title	Location	Date	Organiser(s)	Contribution	Event Type
FAIR Data Management in Life Sciences	Online	14-16 June 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Course
Life Science Data Management: Planning workshop	Online	26-27 September 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Workshop
Life Science Data Management: Planning workshop	Online	4-5 April 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Workshop
Handling Pandemic Omics Data in the Nordics	Online	18-19 May 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, SE, ES; NeIC	Organisation, talks	Symposium
Data management in practice with FAIRDOME-SEEK	Online	9 May 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, UK, DE, BE; DLN	Organisation, talks	Community meeting
Exemplar DMPs in DSW	Online	8 April 2022	BioMedData ELIXIR-NO	Organisation, talks	Webinar
Data management in practice with FAIRDOME-SEEK	Online	17 October 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, UK, DE, BE; DLN	Organisation, talks	Community meeting
BioMedData Face2Face meeting	Sørum	23-25 May 2022	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO	Organisation, talks	Retreat
NBS contact meeting	Tromsø	10-13 February 2022	NBS	Plenary & Symposium talks	Conference
RDA Workshop: kompetanse for forskningsdatahåndtering i Norske fag- og forskningsbibliotek	Online	25 January 2022	RDA Norway	Talk	Workshop
Data-Interopability Platform F2F	Switzerland, Online	28-30 November 2022	ELIXIR	Participation to discussion	Meeting
CCBIOg06 Cancer Genomics	Bergen	22 February 2022	UiB, CCBIO	Lecture	PhD course
Bergen forskningsdata, lunsjseminar	Bergen	March, September 2022	UiB	Presentation	Seminar
Oslo Bioinformatics	Oslo	12	UiO	Workshop	Workshop

Workshop Week 2022 - Create a data management plan with DSW		December 2022			
8th NorMIC Workshop on Biological Optical Microscopy	Oslo, Hybrid	12 January 2023	NALMIN, NorMIC	Lecture	Course
BT8121 - Transdisciplinary biotechnology	Selbu, Hybrid	9 December 2022	DLN	Lecture	Course
Workshop om kompetanse for forskningsdatahåndtering i Norske fag og forskningsbibliotek	Virtual	25 January 2022	RDA Norway	Presentation	Workshop
Global Alliance for Genomic and Health plenary 2022 (GA4GH)	Barcelona	September 2022	GA4GH	Discussion	Plenary
The Rise of the Data Stewards	Online	28 October 2022	RDA-NO, Open Access Week Norway	Talk	Webinar
Pandemi, mangfold og sosial ulikhet	Bergen	27-28 October 2022	Pandemisenteret UiB	Talk	Conference
BioMedData stakeholder meeting in Oslo	Oslo	22.-23.11.2023	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Stakeholder meeting
European RDM Community meeting	Bergen	4-6 December 2023	ELIXIR-EU RDM community	Organisation, talks	Community meeting
Create and Handle Data Management Plans with the Data Stewardship Wizard	Oslo	13 January 2023	Digital Scholarship Center, USIT, Carpentry@UiO, Coderefinery, dScience, Simula, Data Managers Network at UiO, ELIXIR Oslo, Norway's Reproducibility Network (norrn) and UiO Library	Organisation, talks	Workshop
LS RDM group meetup	Online	18 January	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Community

		2023			meeting
LS RDM group meetup	Online	22 February 2023	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Community meeting
LS RDM group meetup	Online	15 March 2023	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Community meeting
LS RDM group meetup	Online	12 April 2023	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Community meeting
Webinar: Open Science Recommendations in the Life Sciences	Online	31 January 2023	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Webinar
Arendalsuka: Regler for åpen deling av data - til hjelp eller hinder?	Arendal, online	17 August 2023	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Public outreach
Life Science RDM course (For institutions in Norway)	Online	06 October-10 November 2023	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Course
Life Science Data Management: Planning workshop	Online	21-22 August 2023	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO, DLN	Organisation, talks	Workshop
BioMedData workshop	Bergen	24 August 2023	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Workshop
Data Management Workshop for the core facility staff across NorSeq nodes	Virtual	29 August 2023	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Workshop
Oslo Bioinformatics Workshop Week - DSW	Oslo	13 December 2023	BioMedData, ELIXIR-NO	Organisation, talks	Workshop
Danish e-infrastructure Consortium (DeiC) conference 2023	Denmark	08 November 2023	DeiC	Talk	Conference
Rltrain: Data Management	Online	6 June - 7 July 2023	European School for Management of Research Infrastructures	Talk, exercises	Course
Bring Your Own Data workshop	Trondheim	11-12 May 2023	Centre for Digital Life Norway	Talk, exercises	Workshop
Transdisciplinary workshop on CyTOF	Bergen	30 May 2023	Centre for Digital Life Norway	Talk	Symposium

Annual meeting: National network of Advanced Proteomics Infrastructure	Bergen	30 May 2023	NAPI	Lecture	Conference
Collaborative Software Development School	Bergen	19-30 June 2023	UiB Dlab	Talk	Summer school
FAIR data management - CanCell	Oslo	9 February 2023	UiO CanCell	Presentation	Course
Data Managers Network UiO board meeting	Oslo	14 February 2023	UiO University Library	Discussion	Community Board Meeting
Data Managers Network UiO board meeting	Oslo	22 August 2023	UiO University Library	Discussion	Community Board Meeting
Data Managers Network UiO board meeting	Oslo	7 December 2023	University Library UiO	Discussion	Community Board Meeting
Oslo Centre for Biostatistics and Epidemiology meeting	Oslo	27 February	UiO, OCBE (Frigessi, Zucknick)	Presentation	Symposium
International Data Week 2023 (incl. RDA plenary)	Salzburg	23-26 October 2023	RDA	Poster	Plenary
EOSC-Nordic Result Transfer Kick Off mtg	Virtual	29 March 2023	EOSC Nordic	Presentation	Kick-off
Data Manager Network UiO meeting	Oslo	28 September 2023	UiO University Library	Discussion	Community meeting
European Health Research Infrastructures Meeting	Oslo	28 September 2023	UiO, OUS	Presentation	Symposium
ELIXIR Data & Interoperability Platforms: F2F Meeting (Hybrid) - 2023	Amsterdam + Virtual	23 November 2023	ELIXIR Hub	Discussion	Meeting
Data Manager Network UiO meeting	Oslo	7 December 2023	UiO University Library	Presentation	Community meeting
UiO:LifeScience convergence environments	Oslo	25 April 2023	UiO:LifeScience	Presentation	Symposium

List of upcoming activities

Event Title	Location	Date	Organiser(s)	Contribution	Event Type
How do people use Electronic Lab Notebooks?	Oslo	18 April 2024	Data Managers Network UiO	Organisation	Community Meeting
Life Sciences RDM Group Meetup: Data Steward career pathway	Online	7 May 2024	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Community Event (Panel Discussion)
Life Science Data Management: Planning workshop	Online	5-6 June 2024	BioMedData	Organisation, talks	Workshop
PhD Course (Collaboration with NORBIS)	In-person	2-5 September 2024	BioMedData & NORBIS	Organisation, lectures	Course
BioMedData: Coordination of post-project period	In-person, TBD	October 2024	BioMedData	Organisation, moderation	Community meeting

Outcomes

The main beneficiaries of these events are the professionals involved in data stewardship, including researchers, data managers, and other stakeholders in the life science domain. The benefits include enhanced skills in data management, increased awareness of FAIR principles, collaboration and coordination within the data stewardship community, and improvements to data management routines across life science research infrastructures in Norway.

Based on the outcomes of these events and feedback from participants, we plan to continue to organise training and capacity building events for data stewards, promote the implementation of FAIR data principles across the Norwegian life science landscape, and strengthen the integration of data management best practices into research workflows. The extension of these activities beyond the currently provided level will depend on available funding streams.

One important aspect is to strengthen the profile of Data Stewards and foster better integration of this new profession at institutional and organisational level, as this will help facilitate collaboration more smoothly between data experts and researchers as well as developers to ensure efficient data management practices that align with a data lifecycle. The aim is also to raise awareness of data stewardship and promote the profession by incorporating into higher education courses for university students and staff in Norway.